

Analysis of the Two Main Equations – 8 Theory

O Manor

April 17, 2021

Abstract:

In this paper, we are going to use the 8 Theory framework to examine the terms in our framework which is a varying Lorenz manifold, $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. Such a manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. The arbitrary variation term has been discretized and partitioned $\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ to create threefold combination of two distinct elements varying in a. The second equation is the coupling constant series, which describe the propagation bosonic fields from fermion clusters, analysis of the first representation will be made.

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

As a varying topology over time, independently from the matrix. It is a separate space, which $\partial g / \partial t$ do not obey the same rules as the matrix. $\partial M / \partial g$ Varying matrix according to a varying topology. The term describes the bosonic and fermionic fields manifesting in our matrix, as we can associate bosonic ripple based on the variation of the second term from the right. $\partial s / \partial M$ How does the varying matrix effect the manifold itself $s = (M, g_E)$. $\partial L / \partial s$ The last term, how does the varying manifold effect the dimension of length. It is a varying curvature framework in which arbitrary variation vanish into matter, and net variations on the manifold are isomorphic to bosonic propagations. We partitioned and discretized the term $\delta g = 0$ and after doing so, derived that there must be an even amount of two distinct elements that differ in sign and form a group due to their varying nature.

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$0: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0 \quad (1.181)$$

We proved that in order to bring the element back to where it was and to attach it to itself it takes an additional map on the varying element, to a threefold combination.

$$Y: \delta g2 \rightarrow \delta g1 \quad (1.182)$$

$$\delta g1(0)\delta g2(Y)\delta g1 \quad (1.183)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.01)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.011)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.012)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

The $2N(\)$ terms refer to a hadronic structure, perfectly symmetrical to vanish into matter, as it is two and three divisible. The invariant (3) element is a symmetry-breaking operator causing a destabilization. Such a factor than yields a net variation, N_V , isomorphic to primes or one, and associated with bosonic propagation fields, which are infinite in kind.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)